

ON WEAKLY Δ -NORMAL SPACES IN TOPOLOGICAL SPACES

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Abstract. The aim of this paper is to study the class of weakly Δ -normal spaces. The relationships among Δ -normal, $w\Delta$ -normal, $w\Delta$ -normal, π -normal, softly normal, silky normal, quasi normal, almost normal, nearly normal, ii-normal, s-normal, α -normal, γ -normal and mildly normal spaces are investigated. Moreover, we introduce the forms of some generalized functions such as almost $g\delta$ -closed and almost $g\delta$ -continuous. We obtain some characterizations and preservation theorems of weakly Δ -normal spaces in the forms of almost generalized δ -closed and almost generalized δ -continuous functions.

Key words and phrases: δ -closed sets; weakly Δ -normal, silky normal, quasi normal, softly normal and ii-normal spaces.

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1. Introduction

In 1968, the notion of quasi normality is a weaker form of normality was introduced by Zaitsev [28]. In 1970, the concept of almost normality was introduced by Singal and Arya [24]. In 1973, the notion of mild normality was introduced by Shchepin [22] and Singal and Singal [25] independently. In 1978, Maheshwari and Prasad [15] introduced a new class of normal spaces is called s-normal spaces in topological spaces and obtained their characterizations. In 1990, Lal and Rahman [13] further investigated the notions of quasi normal and mildly normal spaces. In 1998, the concept of nearly normal space is a weaker form of normal space was introduced by Mukherjee and Debray [17]. In 2000, Dontchev and Noiri [6] introduced the notion of πg -closed sets and by using these sets, obtained a new characterization of quasi normal space. In 2007, Ekici [8] introduced the concept of γ -normal spaces in topological spaces and obtained their properties. In 2008, π -normal topological spaces were introduced by Kalantan [10]. In 2009, Benchalli and Patil [3] introduced a new class of normal spaces is called α -normal spaces in topological spaces and obtained their characterizations. In 2009, Das [5] introduced the concepts of some new classes of normal spaces are called Δ -normal, weakly Δ -normal (briefly $w\Delta$ -normal), and weakly functionally Δ -normal (briefly $wf\Delta$ -normal) spaces and obtained a relation with other weaker versions of normal spaces. Some variants of normality which lies between normal and mildly normal spaces are considered and interrelation among these variants of normality is established by Das [5]. In 2015, Sharma and Kumar [21] introduced a new class of normal spaces is called softly normal spaces in topological spaces and obtained their characterizations. In 2019, Kumar [11] introduced the concept of silky normal spaces in topological spaces and obtained their characterizations. Recently, Kumar [12] introduced a new class of normal spaces is called ii-normal spaces in topological spaces and obtained their characterizations.

2. Preliminaries

Throughout this paper, spaces (X, \mathfrak{T}) , (Y, σ) , and (Z, γ) (or simply X , Y and Z) always mean topological spaces on which no separation axioms are assumed unless explicitly stated. Let A be a subset of a space X . The closure of A and interior of A are denoted by $cl(A)$ and $int(A)$ respectively. A subset A is said to be **regular open** (resp. **regular closed**) if $A = int(cl(A))$ (resp. $A = cl(int(A))$). The family of regular open (resp. regular closed) sets of a space X is denoted by $RO(X)$ (resp. $RC(X)$). The finite union of regular open sets is said to be **π -open** [28]. The complement of a π -open set is said to be **π -closed**. A subset A is said to be **δ -open** [27] set if it is the union of regular open sets. The complement of a δ -open set is said to be **δ -closed** (or A subset A is said to be **δ -closed**

if $A = \delta\text{-cl}(A)$, where $\delta\text{-cl}(A) = \{x \in X : \text{int}(\text{cl}(U)) \cap A \neq \emptyset, U \in \mathfrak{T} \text{ and } x \in U\}$ and the complement of a δ -closed set is said to be **δ -open**).

2.1 Remark. For a subset of a space, we have following implications:

$$\text{regular open} \Rightarrow \pi\text{-open} \Rightarrow \delta\text{-open} \Rightarrow \text{open}$$

Where none of the implications is reversible as shown in [6].

2.2 Definition. A subset A of a space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be

(a) **generalized closed** (briefly **g-closed**) [14] if $\text{cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in \mathfrak{T}$.

(b) **$g\delta$ -closed** [7] if $\text{cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is δ -open in X .

(c) **πg -closed** [6] if $\text{cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is π -open in X .

(d) **rg-closed** [20] if $\text{cl}(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is regular open in X .

(e) **g-open** (resp. **$g\delta$ -open**, **πg -open**, **rg-open**) set if the complement of A is g-closed (resp. $g\delta$ -closed, πg -closed, rg-closed).

2.3 Remark. We have the following implications for the properties of subsets:

$$\text{closed} \Rightarrow \text{g-closed} \Rightarrow g\delta\text{-closed} \Rightarrow \pi g\text{-closed} \Rightarrow \text{rg-closed}$$

Where none of the implications is reversible as can be seen from the following examples:

2.4 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{b\}$ is g-closed as well as $g\delta$ -closed but not closed.

2.5 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{a, c\}$ is $g\delta$ -closed as well as πg -closed. But A is not closed.

2.6 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{a, b\}$ is rg-closed but not πg -closed.

3. Weakly Δ -normal spaces

3.1 Definition. A topological space X is said to be

1. silky normal [11] if for every pair of disjoint subsets A and B of X , one of which is π -closed and the other is δ -closed, there exist disjoint open sets U and V of X such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$.

2. ii-normal [12] (resp. **α -normal** [3], **s-normal** [15], **γ -normal** [8]) if for every pair of disjoint closed subsets A and B of X , there exist disjoint ii-open (resp. α -open, s-open, γ -open) sets U and V of X such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$.

3. quasi normal [28] if for every pair of disjoint π -closed subsets A and B of X , there exist disjoint open sets U and V of X such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$.

4. mildly normal [22, 25] if for every pair of disjoint regularly closed subsets A and B of X , there exist disjoint open sets U and V of X such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$.

5. almost normal [24] if for every pair of disjoint sets A and B of X , one of which is closed and the other is regularly closed, there exist disjoint open sets U and V of X such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$.

6. π -normal [10] if for any two disjoint closed subsets A and B of X , one of which is π -closed, there exist two disjoint open sets U and V of X such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$.

7. softly normal [21] if for any two disjoint subsets A and B of X , one of which is π -closed and the other is regularly closed, there exist disjoint open sets U and V of X such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$.

8. nearly normal [17] if for any pair of nonempty disjoint sets A and B of X , one of which is δ -closed and the other is regularly closed, there exist disjoint open sets U and V of X such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$.

9. Δ -normal [5] if for every pair of disjoint closed sets one of which is δ -closed are contained in disjoint open sets.

10. weakly Δ -normal (briefly **w Δ -normal [5]**) if for every pair of disjoint δ -closed sets are contained in disjoint open sets.

11. weakly functionally Δ -normal (briefly **wf Δ -normal [5]**) if for every pair of disjoint δ -closed sets A and B , there exists a continuous function $f : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that $f(A) = 0$ and $f(B) = 1$.

The following implications are obvious from the definitions and above observations.

Where none of the implications is reversible as can be seen in [11].

3.2 Theorem. For a space X , the following are equivalent:

- X is weakly Δ -normal.
- For every pair of δ -open subsets U and V of X whose union is X , there exist closed subsets G and H of X such that $G \subset U$, $H \subset V$ and $G \cup H = X$.
- For any δ -closed set A and every δ -open set B in X such that $A \subset B$, there exists a open subset U of X such that $A \subset U \subset \text{cl}(U) \subset B$.
- For every pair of disjoint δ -closed subsets A and B of X , there exist open subsets U and V of X such that $A \subset U$, $B \subset V$ and $\text{cl}(U) \cap \text{cl}(V) = \emptyset$.

Proof. (a) \Rightarrow (b), (b) \Rightarrow (c), (c) \Rightarrow (d) and (d) \Rightarrow (a).

(a) \Rightarrow (b). Let U and V be any δ -open subsets of a weakly Δ -normal space X such that $U \cup V = X$. Then, $X - U$ and $X - V$ are disjoint δ -closed subsets of X . By weakly Δ -normality of X , there exist disjoint open subsets U_1 and V_1 of X such that $X - U \subset U_1$ and $X - V \subset V_1$. Let $G = X - U_1$ and $H = X - V_1$. Then, G and H are closed subsets of X such that $G \subset U$, $H \subset V$ and $G \cup H = X$.

(b) \Rightarrow (c). Let A be a δ -closed and B is a δ -open subsets of X such that $A \subset B$. Then, $X - A$ and B are δ -open subsets of X such that $(X - A) \cup B = X$. Then, by part (b), there exist closed sets G and H of X such that $G \subset (X - A)$, $H \subset B$ and $G \cup H = X$. Then, $A \subset (X - G)$, $(X - B) \subset (X - H)$ and $(X - G) \cap (X - H) = \emptyset$. Let $U = X$

– G and $V = (X - H)$. Then U and V are disjoint open sets such that $A \subset U \subset X - V \subset B$. Since $X - V$ is closed, then we have $\text{cl}(U) \subset (X - V)$. Thus, $A \subset U \subset \text{cl}(U) \subset B$.

(c) \Rightarrow (d). Let A and B be any disjoint δ -closed subset of X . Then $A \subset X - B$, where $X - B$ is δ -open. By the part (c), there exists an open subset U of X such that $A \subset U \subset \text{cl}(U) \subset X - B$. Let $V = X - \text{cl}(U)$. Then, V is an open subset of X . Thus, we obtain $A \subset U$, $B \subset V$ and $\text{cl}(U) \cap \text{cl}(V) = \emptyset$.

(d) \Rightarrow (a). It is obvious.

3.3 Proposition. Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be a function, then:

- (a) The image of open subset under an open continuous function is open.
- (b) The inverse image of open (resp. closed) subset under an open continuous function is open (resp. closed) subset.
- (c) The image of closed subset under an open and a closed continuous surjective function is open.

3.4 Theorem. The image of a weakly Δ -normal space under an open continuous injective function is a weakly Δ -normal.

Proof. Let X be a weakly Δ -normal space and let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be an open continuous injective function. We need to show that $f(X)$ is a weakly Δ -normal. Let A and B be any two disjoint δ -closed sets in $f(X)$. Since the inverse image of a δ -closed set under an open continuous function is a δ -closed. Then, $f^{-1}(A)$ and $f^{-1}(B)$ are disjoint δ -closed sets in X . By weakly Δ -normality of X , there exist open subsets U and V of X such that $f^{-1}(A) \subset U$, $f^{-1}(B) \subset V$ and $U \cap V = \emptyset$. Since f is an open continuous injective function, we have $A \subset f(U)$, $B \subset f(V)$ and $f(U) \cap f(V) = \emptyset$. By **Proposition 3.3**, we obtain $f(U)$ and $f(V)$ are disjoint open sets in $f(X)$ such that $A \subset f(U)$ and $B \subset f(V)$. Hence $f(X)$ is weakly Δ -normal.

From the above theorem, we have the following corollary.

3.5 Corollary. Weakly Δ -normality is a topological property.

The following lemma helps us to show that weakly Δ -normality is a hereditary with respect to closed domain subspaces.

3.6 Lemma. Let M be a closed domain subspace of a space X . If A is a open set in X , then $A \cap M$ is open set in M .

3.7 Theorem. Weakly Δ -normality is a hereditary with respect to closed domain subspaces.

Proof. Let M be a closed domain subspace of a weakly Δ -normal space X . Let A and B be any disjoint δ -closed sets in M . Since M is a closed domain subspace of X , then we have A and B be any disjoint δ -closed sets of X . By weakly Δ -normal of X , there exist disjoint open subsets U and V of X such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$. By the **Lemma 3.6**, we obtain $U \cap M$ and $V \cap M$ are disjoint open sets in M such that $A \subset U \cap M$ and $B \subset V \cap M$. Hence, M is weakly Δ -normal subspace.

Since every closed and open (clopen) subset is a closed domain, then we have the following corollary.

3.8 Corollary. Weakly Δ -normality is a hereditary with respect to clopen subspaces.

3.9 Lemma. A subset A of a space X is $g\delta$ -open iff $F \subset \text{int}(A)$ whenever F is δ -closed and $F \subset A$.

The following result is useful for giving some other characterizations of weakly Δ -normal spaces.

3.10 Theorem. For a space X , the following are equivalent:

- (a) X is weakly Δ -normal.
- (b) For any disjoint δ -closed sets H and K , there exist disjoint g -open sets U and V such that $H \subset U$ and $K \subset V$.
- (c) For any disjoint δ -closed sets H and K , there exist disjoint $g\delta$ -open sets U and V such that $H \subset U$ and $K \subset V$.
- (d) For any δ -closed set H and any δ -open set V containing H , there exists a g -open set U of X such that $H \subset U \subset \text{cl}(U) \subset V$.
- (e) For any δ -closed set H and any δ -open set V containing H , there exists a $g\delta$ -open set U of X such that $H \subset U \subset \text{cl}(U) \subset V$.

Proof. (a) \Rightarrow (b), (b) \Rightarrow (c), (c) \Rightarrow (d), (d) \Rightarrow (e) and (e) \Rightarrow (a).

(a) \Rightarrow (b). Let X be weakly Δ -normal space. Let H, K be disjoint δ -closed sets of X . By assumption, there exist disjoint open sets U, V such that $H \subset U$ and $K \subset V$. Since every open set is g -open. So, U and V are g -open sets such that $H \subset U$ and $K \subset V$.

(b) \Rightarrow (c). Let H, K be two disjoint δ -closed sets. By assumption, there exist disjoint g -open sets U and V such that $H \subset U$ and $K \subset V$. Since g -open set is $g\delta$ -open. So, U and V are $g\delta$ -open sets such that $H \subset U$ and $K \subset V$.

(c) \Rightarrow (d). Let H be any δ -closed set and V be any δ -open set containing H . By assumption, there exist disjoint $g\delta$ -open sets U and W such that $H \subset U$ and $X - V \subset W$. By **Lemma 3.9**, we get $X - V \subset \text{int}(W)$ and $\text{cl}(U) \cap \text{int}(W) = \emptyset$. Hence $H \subset U \subset \text{cl}(U) \subset X - \text{int}(W) \subset V$.

(d) \Rightarrow (e). Let H be any δ -closed set and V be any δ -open set containing H . By assumption, there exist g -open set U of X such that $H \subset U \subset \text{cl}(U) \subset V$. Since, every g -open set is $g\delta$ -open, there exists $g\delta$ -open sets U of X such that $H \subset U \subset \text{cl}(U) \subset V$.

(e) \Rightarrow (a). Let H, K be any two disjoint δ -closed sets of X . Then $H \subset X - K$ and $X - K$ is δ -open. By assumption, there exists $g\delta$ -open set G of X such that $H \subset G \subset \text{cl}(G) \subset X - K$. Put $U = \text{int}(G)$, $V = X - \text{cl}(G)$. Then U and V are disjoint open sets of X such that $H \subset U$ and $K \subset V$.

4. Some continuous and closed functions

4.1 Definition. A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is said to be

- (a) **completely continuous** [1] if $f^{-1}(F)$ is regular closed in X for every closed set F of Y .
- (b) **super continuous** [18] if $f^{-1}(F)$ is δ -closed in X for every closed set F of Y .
- (c) **R-map** [4] if $f^{-1}(F)$ is regular closed in X for every regular closed set F of Y .
- (d) **almost continuous** [23] if $f^{-1}(F)$ is closed in X for every regular closed set F of Y .
- (e) **δ -continuous** [19] if $f^{-1}(F)$ is δ -closed in X for every regular closed set F of Y .

(f) π -continuous [6] (resp. almost π -continuous [6]) if $f^{-1}(F)$ is π -closed in X for every closed (resp. regular closed) set F of Y .

(g) g -continuous [2] (resp. almost g -continuous [9]) if $f^{-1}(F)$ is g -closed in X for every closed (resp. regular closed) set F of Y .

(h) $g\delta$ -continuous [16] (resp. almost $g\delta$ -continuous) if $f^{-1}(F)$ is $g\delta$ -closed in X for every closed (resp. regular closed) set F of Y .

From the definitions stated above, we obtained the following diagram:

None of the implications in above Diagram is reversible as shown by the following examples.

4.2 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$, $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{a\}, X\}$, $Y = \{p, q\}$ and $\rho = \{\phi, \{p\}, Y\}$. Let the identity function $f : (X, \mathfrak{T}) \rightarrow (X, \rho)$ be defined by $f(a) = f(c) = q$, $f(b) = p$. Then, the function f is g -continuous as well as almost g -continuous but it is not continuous.

4.3 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$, $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$ and $\rho = \{\phi, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$. Then the identity function $f : (X, \mathfrak{T}) \rightarrow (X, \rho)$ is R-map as well as δ -continuous but not continuous.

4.4 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$, $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, X\}$ and $\rho = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$. Then the identity function $f : (X, \mathfrak{T}) \rightarrow (X, \rho)$ is continuous as well as g -continuous but not δ -continuous.

4.5 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$, $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$. The identity function $f : (X, \mathfrak{T}) \rightarrow (X, \mathfrak{T})$ is defined as $f(a) = f(b) = a$ and $f(c) = c$. Then the function f is π -continuous as well as continuous but not R-map.

4.6 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, X\}$. Let the identity function $f : (X, \mathfrak{T}) \rightarrow (X, \mathfrak{T})$ defined by $f(a) = c$, $f(b) = a$, $f(c) = b$, $f(d) = c$. Then the function f is almost πg -continuous but it is not almost g -continuous. If we take the function f as $f(a) = a$, $f(b) = d$, $f(c) = b$, $f(d) = a$ then the function f is πg -continuous but it is not g -continuous.

4.7 Definition. A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is said to be

(a) **g -closed** [6] (resp. **$g\delta$ -closed**, **πg -closed** [6]) if $f(F)$ is g -closed (resp. $g\delta$ -closed, πg -closed) in Y for every closed set F of X .

(b) **rc-preserving** [6] (resp. **almost closed** [23], **almost g -closed** [6], **almost $g\delta$ -closed**, **almost πg -closed** [6]) if $f(F)$ is regular closed (resp. closed, g -closed, $g\delta$ -closed, πg -closed) in Y for every $F \in RC(X)$.

From the definitions stated above, we obtained the following diagram:

None of the implications in above Diagram is reversible as shown by the following examples.

4.8 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$, $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{c\}, X\}$ and $\rho = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$. Then the identity function $f : (X, \mathfrak{T}) \rightarrow (X, \rho)$ is rg-closed but it is not π g-closed.

4.9 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$, $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$ and $\rho = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, X\}$. Then the identity function $f : (X, \mathfrak{T}) \rightarrow (X, \rho)$ is π g-closed but it is not almost g-closed, since $\{a, c\} \in \text{RC}(X, \mathfrak{T})$ but $f(\{a, c\})$ is not g-closed in (X, ρ) . Moreover, $f^{-1} : (X, \rho) \rightarrow (X, \mathfrak{T})$ is almost closed but it is not rg-closed. Clearly $\{b\}$ is closed in (X, ρ) but $f^{-1}(\{b\})$ is not rg-closed in (X, \mathfrak{T}) .

4.10 Theorem. If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is a δ -continuous and $\text{g}\delta$ -closed function, then $f(A)$ is $\text{g}\delta$ -closed in Y for every $\text{g}\delta$ -closed set A of X .

Proof. Let A be any $\text{g}\delta$ -closed set of X and V be any δ -open set of Y containing $f(A)$. Since f is δ -continuous, $f^{-1}(V)$ is δ -open in X and $A \subset f^{-1}(V)$. Therefore, we have $\text{cl}(A) \subset f^{-1}(V)$ and hence $f(\text{cl}(A)) \subset V$. Since f is $\text{g}\delta$ -closed, $f(\text{cl}(A))$ is $\text{g}\delta$ -closed in Y and hence we obtain $\text{cl}(f(A)) \subset \text{cl}(f(\text{cl}(A))) \subset V$. Hence $f(A)$ is $\text{g}\delta$ -closed in Y .

4.11 Theorem. A surjection $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is almost $\text{g}\delta$ -closed if and only if for each subset S of Y and each $U \in \text{RO}(X)$ containing $f^{-1}(S)$, there exists a $\text{g}\delta$ -open set V of Y such that $S \subset V$ and $f^{-1}(V) \subset U$.

Proof. Necessity. Suppose that f is almost $\text{g}\delta$ -closed. Let S be a subset of Y and $U \in \text{RO}(X)$ containing $f^{-1}(S)$. If $V = Y - f(X - U)$, then V is a $\text{g}\delta$ -open set of Y such that $S \subset V$ and $f^{-1}(V) \subset U$.

Sufficiency. Let F be any regular closed set of X . Then $f^{-1}(Y - f(F)) \subset (X - F)$ and $(X - F) \in \text{RO}(X)$. There exists a $\text{g}\delta$ -open set V of Y such that $Y - f(F) \subset V$ and $f^{-1}(V) \subset (X - F)$. Therefore, we have $f(F) \supset (Y - V)$ and $F \subset X - f^{-1}(V) \subset f^{-1}(Y - V)$. Hence, we obtain $f(F) = Y - V$ and $f(F)$ is $\text{g}\delta$ -closed in Y . This shows that f is almost $\text{g}\delta$ -closed.

5. Preservation theorems

5.1 Theorem. If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is an almost $g\delta$ -continuous, rc-preserving injection and Y is weakly Δ -normal, then X is weakly Δ -normal.

Proof. Let A and B be any disjoint δ -closed sets of X . Since f is an rc-preserving injection, $f(A)$ and $f(B)$ are disjoint δ -closed sets of Y . Since Y is weakly Δ -normal, there exist disjoint open sets U and V of Y such that $f(A) \subset U$ and $f(B) \subset V$.

Now, if $G = \text{int}(\text{cl}(U))$ and $H = \text{int}(\text{cl}(V))$. Then G and H are regular open sets such that $f(A) \subset G$ and $f(B) \subset H$. Since f is almost $g\delta$ -continuous, $f^{-1}(G)$ and $f^{-1}(H)$ are disjoint $g\delta$ -open sets containing A and B , respectively. It follows from **Theorem 3.10**, that X is weakly Δ -normal.

5.2 Theorem. If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is a super continuous, almost g -closed surjection and X is weakly Δ -normal space, then Y is normal.

Proof. Let A and B be any two disjoint closed sets of Y . Then $f^{-1}(A)$ and $f^{-1}(B)$ are disjoint δ -closed sets of X . Since X is weakly Δ -normal, there exist disjoint open sets U and V such that $f^{-1}(A) \subset U$ and $f^{-1}(B) \subset V$.

Let $G = \text{int}(\text{cl}(U))$ and $H = \text{int}(\text{cl}(V))$. Then G and H are disjoint regular open sets of X such that $f^{-1}(A) \subset G$ and $f^{-1}(B) \subset H$. Now, we set $K = Y - f(X - G)$ and $L = Y - f(X - H)$. Then K and L are g -open sets of Y such that $A \subset K$, $B \subset L$, $f^{-1}(K) \subset G$ and $f^{-1}(L) \subset H$. Since G and H are disjoint, so are K and L . Since K and L are g -open and we obtain $A \subset \text{int}(K)$, $B \subset \text{int}(L)$ and $\text{int}(K) \cap \text{int}(L) = \emptyset$. This shows that Y is normal.

5.3 Theorem. Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be an δ -continuous (resp. almost continuous) and almost $g\delta$ -closed surjection. If X is weakly Δ -normal (resp. normal) space, then Y is weakly Δ -normal.

Proof. Let A and B be any disjoint δ -closed sets of Y . Then $f^{-1}(A)$ and $f^{-1}(B)$ are disjoint δ -closed (resp. closed) sets of X . Since X is weakly Δ -normal (resp. normal), there exist disjoint open sets U and V of X such that $f^{-1}(A) \subset U$ and $f^{-1}(B) \subset V$.

Put $G = \text{int}(\text{cl}(U))$ and $H = \text{int}(\text{cl}(V))$. Then G and H are disjoint regular open sets of X such that $f^{-1}(A) \subset G$ and $f^{-1}(B) \subset H$. By **Theorem 4.11**, there exist $g\delta$ -open sets K and L of Y such that $A \subset K$, $B \subset L$, $f^{-1}(K) \subset G$ and $f^{-1}(L) \subset H$. Since G and H are disjoint, so are K and L . It follows from **Theorem 3.9**, that Y is weakly Δ -normal.

5.4 Corollary. If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is an almost continuous and almost closed surjection and X is a normal space, then Y is weakly Δ -normal.

Proof. Since every almost closed function is almost $g\delta$ -closed. Therefore, the proof is obvious by **Theorem 5.3**.

REFERENCES

1. S. P. Arya and R. Gupta, On strongly continuous mappings, *Kyungpook Math. J.* **14**(1974), 131-143.
2. K. Balachandran, P. Sundaram and H. Maki, On generalized continuous maps in topological spaces, *Mem. Fac. Sci. Kochi Univ. Ser. A (Math.)*, **12**(1991), 5-13.
3. S. S. Benchalli and P. G. Patil, Some new continuous maps in topological spaces, *Journal of Advanced Studies in Topology*, **2/1-2**, (2009), 53-63.
4. D. Carnahan, Some properties related to compactness in topological spaces, Ph. D. Thesis, Univ. of Arkansas (1973).
5. A. K. Das, Δ -normal spaces and decompositions of normality, *Applied Gen. Topol.*, **10**(2), (2009), 197-206.
6. J. Dontchev and T. Noiri, Quasi normal spaces and πg -closed sets, *Acta Math Hungar.* **89**(3)(2000), 211-219.
7. J. Dontchev I. Arokiarani and K. Balachandran, On generalized δ -closed sets and almost weakly Hausdorff spaces, Q and A in *General Topology*, **18**(2000), 17-30.
8. E. Ekici, On γ -normal spaces, *Bull. Math. Soc. Sci. Math. Roumanie Tome*, 50(98), **3**(2007), 259-272.
9. E. Ekici and C. W. Baker, On πg -closed sets and continuity, *Kochi J. Math.*, **2**(2007), 35-42.
10. L. Kalantan, π -normal topological spaces, *Filomat*, Vol. **22**, No. 1 (2008), 173-181.
11. H. Kumar, Silky normal spaces in topological spaces, *Jou. of Emer. Tech. and Innov. Res.*, Vol. 6, Issue 6, (2019), 233-240.
12. H. Kumar, η -normal spaces in topological spaces, *Jou. of Emer. Tech. and Innov. Res.*, Vol. 7, Issue 8, (2020), 1510-1520.
13. S. Lal and M. S. Rahman, A note on quasi-normal spaces, *Indian J. Math.*, **32**(1990), 87-94.
14. N. Levine, Generalized closed sets in topology, *Rend. Circ. Mat. Palermo (2)*, **19**(1970), 89-96.
15. S. N. Maheshwari and R. Prasad, On s -normal spaces, *Bull. Math. Soc. Sci. Math. R. S. Roumanie (N. S.)*, **22** (68) (1978), 27-29.
16. K. Meena and K. Sivakamasundari, Separation axioms by Δ^* -closed sets in topological spaces, *Int. Jour. Math. Anal.*, **9**(19), (2015), 927-934.
17. Mukherjee M. N. and Debray A., On nearly paracompact spaces and nearly full normality, *Mat. Vesnik*, **50**(1998), 99-104.
18. B. M. Munshi and D. S. Bassan, Super continuous functions, *Indian J. Pure Appl. Math.*, **13**(1982), 229-236.
19. T. Noiri, On δ -continuous functions, *J. Korean Math. Soc.*, **16**(1980), 161-166.
20. N. Palaniappan and K. C. Rao, Regular generalized closed sets, *Kyungpook Math. J.* **33**(1993), 211-219.
21. M. C. Sharma and H. Kumar, Softly normal topological spaces, *Acta Ciencia Indica*, Vol. XLI M. No. **2**, (2015), 81-84.
22. Shchepin E. V., Real functions and near normal spaces, *Sibirskii Mat. Zhurnal*, **13**(1972), 1182-1196.
23. M. K. Singal and A. R. Singal, Almost continuous functions, *Yokohama Math. J.* **1**(1968), 63-73.
24. M. K. Singal and S. P. Arya, Almost normal and almost completely regular spaces, *Glasnik Matematički*, Tom 5(25), No. 1, (1970), 141-148.
25. M. K. Singal and A. R. Singal, Mildly normal spaces, *Kyungpook Math. J.* **13**(1973), 27-31.
26. M. Stone, Application of the theory of Boolean rings to general topology, *Transactions of the American Mathematical Society*, **41**(1937), 374-481.
27. N. V. Velicko, H -closed topological spaces, *Amer. Math. Soc. Transl.*, **2**(78), (1968), 103-118.
28. V. Zaitsev, On certain classes of topological spaces and their bicompatifications, *Dokl. Akad. Nauk SSSR*, **178**(1968), 778-779.